

OPTIMIZATION OF DIAGNOSTICS AND PREDICTION OF THE COURSE OF BRONCHOPULMONARY PATHOLOGIES IN CHILDREN, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT METABOLIC CHANGES

Akbarova Muruvvat Sobirovna

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, assistant of the Department of Pharmacology and Physiology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12505708>

Abstract. Acute respiratory diseases (ARI) of the respiratory tract in currently remain one of the most pressing problems pediatrics. According to epidemiological studies of acute respiratory infections, annually suffered by 64% of children under five years of age. The following factors are considered to contribute to the development of OB:diseases and conditions: respiratory viral diseases (influenza,adenoviral infections, respiratory syncytial infections,parainfluenza and a number of other viral diseases).

Keywords: acute bronchitis (AB), Acute respiratory diseases (ARI).

Introduction. Acute bronchitis (AB) - inflammation of the bronchi mainly infectious origin, lasting up to 1 month. Besides,a significant contribution to the formation of OB is made by allergic diseases (including bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis,allergic conjunctivitis), air pollutants (dust, chemical agents), deficiency of local immunity reserve (hypertrophy nasopharyngeal and palatine tonsils,immunodeficiency states),smoking (including passive smoking).

Materials and methods. The diagnosis of acute bronchitis is made in the presence of acute cough lasting no more than 3 weeks, regardless of the presence of sputum in the absence of signs of pneumonia and chronic lung diseases,which can also cause cough.

Laboratory data

- Leukopenia, less commonly leukocytosis with minor band shift left
- Bacteriological (sputum culture) examination;
- Bacterioscopic (Gram stain) examination
- Determination of antibodies to viruses or mycoplasmas, methods direct immunofluorescence on nasal swabs, ELISA,Complement Fixation Reaction upon admission and discharge from hospital.

On chest x-ray, inflammatory changes inThere is no lung tissue (important for differential diagnosis). The most important in the differential diagnosis of OB are pneumonia, whooping cough, bronchial asthma, gastroesophageal reflux(presented below).

Discussions. In recent years, priority positions in the prevention of OB have been taken by vaccination of children, in particular annual influenza vaccination Prevention reduces the incidence of OBA several times. IN within the framework of evidence-based medicine, the most significant indications for Vaccinations should include:

- children with chronic diseases (regardless of age);
- children in closed groups;
- teenagers.

Conclusion. Special studies on the effectiveness of this measure prevention in day hospitals for children showed their high efficiency. The methods presented are described in the

following way:pharmacoepidemiological approaches to assessing the treatment of the most common variants of bronchitis in children: acute (simple) bronchitis,recurrent bronchitis.

REFERENCES

1. Таточенко В.К, Середа Е.В., Фёдоров А.М., Катосова Л.К., Самсыгина Г.А., Дементьева Г.М., Стречунский Л.С., Жапкива Л.П. Антибактериальная терапия пневмонии у детей. // Consilium-Medicum, приложение. — Т. 3. — №8. 2001.(Из:http://www.consiliummedicum.com/media/consilium/01_08c/4.shtml)
2. Харламова Ф.С., Кладова О.В., Легкова Т.П., Фельдфикс Л.И. Профилактика и лечение ОРИ у детей // Педиатрическая фармакология. — 2009.
3. Чучалин А.Г. Актуальные вопросы пульмонологии.// Русский медицинский журнал. — 2000.
4. Gendrel D. Pneumonies communautaires de l'enfant: etiologie et traitement. Arch. Pediatr. 2002; 9 (3):
5. Runkel F. Giessen Mechanist der Wirkung. Pharmazeutische Zeitung 150, Jahrgang, 27 Januar, 2005.